

PROFESSIONAL PREPARATION FOR CURRENT ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS: MAINTAINING INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION COMPETENCE METHODS

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Annotation: The possibilities of using various services, computer programs, electronic educational resources for teaching future English language teachers in specialized groups are considered, examples of created electronic manuals and applications in the process of teaching a foreign language are given.

Keywords: educational resources, the process of teaching a foreign language, the creation of electronic manuals and applications, information and communication competence.

INTRODUCTION

The field of second and foreign language teaching and learning has been an issue of debate for a long time. Various theories and methods of language learning have been introduced. Grammar translation method occupied the field of foreign and second language teaching for many decades and is still of use today. The field has also been dominated by the behaviorist theory and the idea that language is nothing but a social behavior that can be learned as any other behavior through the process of habit formation; and many language drills have been designed for this purpose. Learners may share the same aim of learning a language which is ‘being able to use it effectively’; but which ability is required for that? and how to achieve it? have been questions for both linguists and methodologists!

The modern education system is becoming increasingly dependent on information technology and requires teachers to have a large stock of various knowledge, skills, and the ability to be mobile and keep up with the times. A teacher who owns information and communication technologies (hereinafter referred to as ICT) and introduces them into the educational process improves not only the quality of education, but also their professional skills. With the introduction of ICT, the teacher gets the opportunity to educate himself, develop creatively and strive for professional growth [1].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Terrel and Krahen (2013) have defined communicative competence as the use of language in social communications without grammatical analysis. They related communicative competence to the communication and didn't give a focus for the

grammatical competence. This means that communicative competence is manifested in the communication. They argued that the primary goal of language learning should be the development of the communicative skills.

Today, the teacher must meet the requirements of modern education. To be able not only to select forms and methods for developing interest in the subject being studied, improving the quality of education, but also to be ready for continuous improvement of their knowledge. And the variety of ICT tools that can be used in the learning process: electronic textbooks, dictionaries and reference books, didactic material, presentations, forums for communication and much more - will help to realize educational tasks, to form the competence of a teacher.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The formation of information and communication competence of a teacher occurs in stages [2]:

1. Basic competence (the need to use ICT in the educational process, motivation to obtain the necessary knowledge in this area).
2. General competence (the desire to introduce the acquired knowledge into the educational process, a phased reflection of one's activities in the use of ICT).
3. Professional competence (the desire to transfer the experience gained in the field of ICT to colleagues and students, the desire to participate in the creation and implementation of a program related to informatization of the educational process in an educational institution).

Modern teenagers live in the world of electronic culture, therefore, in my professional work, I strive to constantly search for and introduce modern information and communication technologies into the educational process in order to captivate them with the English language. I try to create conditions for the development of students' creative abilities, teach them to think independently, increase motivation to study the subject, encourage their individual abilities and talents.

One of the priority tasks in education is the development of students' independence, preparing them for adulthood. Today it is very important to educate a person who can easily navigate in the information space. To do this, I study electronic educational resources myself, and then I involve students. After analyzing the curriculum and textbooks on the subject "English", I came to the conclusion that the material of a country-specific nature is not enough. Therefore, I considered it relevant to create, together with the students of the profile group, electronic educational resources that will be useful to both students and teachers.

CONCLUSION

The use of ICT in the educational process allows students to study the subject with interest, to involve them in self-development. Of great importance for the teacher is the formation of his information and communication competence. When the need to use

ICT in the educational process, the motivation to acquire the necessary knowledge in this area develops into a desire to transfer the experience gained in this area to colleagues and students, into a desire to participate in the creation and implementation of a program related to informatization of the educational process in an educational institution, it can be considered that a modern teacher fully complies with the new standards of a necessary, updated, in-demand teacher.

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